

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF SELF-LEARNING MODULES (SLMs) IN GRADE 9 PHYSICS

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Development and Validation of Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) in Grade 9 Physics

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Abstract

Modular instruction was one of the ways that the Department of Education proposes to continue the students' learning despite the COVID-19 pandemic. Modules, as self-learning material, can help students fully understand their lessons during their phases. Physics can be taught or learned effectively if experiments and observations are done. So, this study is aimed to develop and validate a self-learning module in grade 9 physics. Specifically, it sought to determine the following: develop supplementary instructional materials according to the learning competencies in grade 9 physics and validate the SLMs in terms of their acceptability and Readability. Findings revealed that all the evaluators agreed that the SLMs are acceptable according to the following factors: (a) content validity, (b) Format, (c) Presentation and organization, and Accuracy of up-to-date date information since the score given by the evaluators have conformed the set standard score by DepEd. This study uses a descriptive-developmental research design in developing and validating SLM for science nine, specifically in learning projectiles launched horizontally, vertically, and at an angle (S9FE-IVa-34 and S9FE-IVa-35). The descriptive method was utilized to present the qualitative data. Three physics teachers who were considered experts in their fields validated the developed self-learning modules. The result shows that the readability test shows that the modules are relatively easy to read. They are suitable for grades 7-9 because they use plain English that they easily understand.

Keywords: *self-learning modules, physics, validity, readability*

Introduction

Observation and experiment are synonymous with physics (Urone et al., 2020). Many Physicists, like Albert Einstein, created their postulates by performing observations and elaborating on reasoning. Many studies show that this is the best way for students to understand physics maturely (Asrizal, 2021). The NGSS (standards of USA pedagogical practices in K-12 science instruction) also states that physics learning has to require students to engage with and reflect on phenomena and the universe (Calmer, 2019).

As educational leaders, it is thus significant to explore how instructional design can enhance teaching in a traditional learning environment. Instructional design, which involves systematically developing instructional materials and activities, ensures that learners achieve specific learning goals or outcomes reflected in the education curriculum and provides relevant instructions suitable for a wide range of learning environments (Torrefranca, 2017).

Physics has been one of the most challenging subjects in the curriculum. It is challenging. This may be accounted to using mathematics as its language, which requires computation skills. Misunderstandings and misconceptions among students arise when physics concepts are not adequately explained. Physics is an exciting subject because it helps people understand how the world around them works. Physics also discloses understanding and organizing the universe by simply dealing with fundamentals and letting others discover the patterns and connections between seemingly disparate phenomena (Estacio, 2015).

The National Science Education standards require science teachers to use science tools and instructional materials, media, and technological resources accessible to the students to teach the subject matter effectively. Furthermore, the development of the instructional materials must be in students' interests, knowledge, understanding, abilities, needs, and materials in effective instruction.

The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study 2019 (TIMSS) revealed on Tuesday, December 8, that Filipino students lagged behind other countries in the international assessment for mathematics and science for grade 4. The Philippines only scored 297 in mathematics and 249 in science, "significantly lower" than any other participating country. The country achieved the lowest of 58 participating countries for both tests (Magsambol, 2020). These findings only highlight the urgent need to innovate and provide learning packs that address the growing number of difficulties plaguing our educational system. Part of this is due to the increasing burden of providing a high-quality learning experience, particularly in laboratory activities in Physics, which has been an issue not only during the pandemic but also before these trying times. Physics teaching in our country was primarily conducted without experimental bases for a long time. It simply implies that physics instruction almost entirely was and still is in many places today, and it is carried out by lecturing and basic problem-solving procedures on the board. Because of this unsatisfactory quality of teaching, like that of the explanatory and display learning, we see why many students in the Philippines show very little desire and motivation to learn Physics (Sabasales, 2018).

Undoubtedly, we educators must work collaboratively to enrich and rebuild our educational foundation to meet the demands of the modern generation and its ever-increasing needs.

Research Objectives

This study aims to develop and validate a self-learning module for grade 9 physics. Specifically, it sought to determine the following:

1. Develop supplementary instructional materials according to the learning competencies in grade 9 physics,
2. Validate the LSM in terms of:
 - 2.1. Acceptability
 - 2.1.1. Content Validity
 - 2.1.2. Format
 - 2.1.3. Presentation and organization
 - 2.1.4. Accuracy and up-to-date information
 - 2.2. Readability

Methodology

Research Design

This study uses a descriptive-developmental research design to develop and validate SLM for science nine, specifically in learning projectiles launched horizontally, vertically, and at an angle (S9FE-IVa-34 and S9FE-IVa-35). The descriptive method was utilized to present the qualitative data.

Participants

This study involves three expert validators. These validators include a physics professor from a State University, a Physics Instructor from a State University, and a Senior High School Physics teacher. They evaluated the SLM's acceptability in terms of (a) content validity, (b) format, (c) presentation and organization, and (d) accuracy, up-to-date information, and readability.

Instruments

In gathering data relevant to this study, the validators used the Evaluation rating sheet for print resources (DM No. 441s. 2019 Division Guidelines and Processes for LRMS Assessment and Evaluation for localized materials). The SLM was subjected to an online readability test called Style Writer, The Coleman Liau index, Flesch Kincaid Grade Level, ARI (Automated Readability Index), SMOG, and Gunning Fogs readability test are tools for testing.

Procedure

Designing/ Planning Stage

The Self-learning module was created after determining the target learners and the topics. The following procedures were done to achieve the purpose of the study. The first step is to determine the design of the module. The researchers identified the module's essential parts that needed to be included. Each module has the following components which are:

- (1)Overview (Target locked): Learners could determine the lesson's basic overview. This includes a basic explanation of the prerequisite topics before learning the main issue.
- (2)Objectives (target locked): The specific competencies the students need to acquire after answering the SLM.
- (3)Review Activities- These activities measure the learners' basic knowledge about the previous lesson.
- (4)Learning Activities: This includes discussions of the lesson and activities where the learners explore more about the topics.
- (5)Practice Tasks: These consist of exercises that learners apply and review their learning concepts.
- (6)Summative: This was designed to measure the learners' understanding and retention of information that they have learned in the SLM.

The second step was constructing the module itself. The activities were created in accordance with the learning competencies and objectives.

The researchers presented the draft to the adviser and research instructor to validate the SLM initially. Then, the SLMs were edited based on their comments and suggestions. After that, three experts were asked to read and evaluate the modules. The three experts included one physics professor, a physics Instructor, and a Senior High School science teacher.

They examined the modules based on the following predictors (1) Content validity, (2) Format, (3)Presentation, and (4)Accuracy and timeliness of the information. Then, after that, LSM was subjected to an online readability test called online-utility.org. This online tool calculates the readability of the SLM based on the Coleman Liau index, Flesch Kincaid Grade Level, ARI (Automated Readability Index), SMOG, and Gunning Fogs readability test.

Finalization of the developed and validated SLM.

After developing and validating the SLMs, they were finalized based on the evaluation stage results.

Data Analysis

The researchers used descriptive statistics such as percentages, means, and standard deviation to analyze this study's experts' evaluation ratings. Textual interpretation will be used to note the recommendations and suggestions.

Results and Discussion

The Designed SLM (Self-Learning Module)

Two self-learning modules were developed and validated for the two competencies in science 9 Quarter 4. Specifically, module 1 covers the topics of competency code S9FE-IVa—34, horizontal and vertical motions, while module 2 covers the topics of competency code S9FE-IVa-35, motion in two dimensions.

Each module includes the following parts: an overview, objectives, review activities, learning activities, practice tasks, and summative assessments. The researcher ensured that the learners could easily understand the developed modules. Furthermore, the SLM used a variety of instructional guides and simulation activities that could capture students' interest as they answered or learned about the assigned topics.

Validation of the SLM

Table 1. Summary of scores by the validators

	Validator 1		Validator 2		Validator 3		Total mean score	
	SLM 1	SLM 2	SLM 1	SLM 2	SLM 1	SLM 2	SLM 1	SLM 2
Content	26	26	22	22	22	22	23.33	23.33
Format	68	68	71	71	54	54	64.33	64.33
Presentation and organization	19	19	18	18	20	20	19	19
Accuracy and up-to-datedness of the information	23	23	22	22	24	24	23	23

As presented in Table 1, the evaluators' overall average rating on the developed instructional 1 and 2 for factor 1, which is the content, is both 23.33; this score suggests that it passed the standard passing score that DepEd sets, which is at least 21. In factor 2 Format, the mean scores are 64.33 for modules 1 and 2. This score shows that SLM 1 and 2 passed the said criterion because the standard score to pass this criterion is 54 and above.

The standard score for Presentation and organization criteria is at least 15 and above. Table 1 shows that the evaluators' scores on this criterion are both 19. This means that the score passed the set standard. The last factor is the accuracy and up-to-dateness of the information. The standard score for this criterion is 20 and above. The validators' score for both modules is 23, which conforms to the set standard.

All evaluators agreed that SLMs are valid according to their content, format, presentation, organization, accuracy, and up-to-date information. According to the evaluators, the SLM conforms to objectives set by DepEd MELCS, especially module 1. Additional HOTS (Higher-order thinking skills) should be integrated into problem-solving and activities or thought-provoking questions. Also, rubrics or criteria for scoring should be presented in the SLM.

Table 2. Summary of the index scores of the readability test.

Readability Test Tool	Module 1 (Index scores)	Module 2 (Index scores)
Coleman Liau index	7	7
ARI (Automated Readability Index),	9.07	4.4
SMOG	7.3	7.5
Flesh reading ease	65	66.4
Gunning Fog	9.2	9.8

Table 2 shows that modules 1 and 2 have a Coleman Liau index score of 7. Coleman-Liau's readability test focuses on long words and long sentences. According to Coleman-Liau, the standard aim score of a text should be around eight or less. This means that the readability score of the module is suitable for high school students aged 12-14.

The automated readability index (ARI) gives a score that indicates the difficulty of a page to be read. For module 1, the ARI is 9.07, which means it is suitable for grade 8 learners, while module 2 has a lesser ARI, 4.4, which is appropriate only for grade 5 learners. This means Module 2 needs to be revised to be suitable for higher grades.

Another readability test utilized was the SMOG, which focuses on polysyllabic words. Both modules 1 and 2 have almost the same score, 7.3 and 7.5, respectively; this score means that the modules are readable for 7th grade.

The flesh reading ease score shows the difficulty level of the English language used. Modules 1 and 2 have a flesh reading ease score of 65 and 66.4, respectively. The researchers used plain English suitable for grades 8 and 9. As shown in the Gunning Fog index, module 1 and module have an index of 9.2 and 9.8; respectively, this score indicates that the SLMs are relatively easy to read.

The readability test shows that the modules are relatively easy to read overall. They are suitable for grades 7-9 because they use plain English that is easily understood by them.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the developed self-learning modules on Horizontal and vertical motion of projectiles and two-dimensional motion agreed that SLMs are valid according to their content, format, presentation, organization, accuracy, and up-to-date information. According to the evaluators, the SLM conforms to objectives set by DepEd MELCS, especially module 1. Additional HOTS (Higher-order thinking skills) should be integrated into problem-solving and activities or thought-provoking questions. Also, rubrics or criteria for scoring should be presented in the SLM.

On the readability test, the LSMs were fairly easy to read since they use plain English and are suitable for grades 7 to 9. This means that the SLM is easily understood by grade 9 students, who are the target learners who will use it.

Based on the results shown in this study, the researcher recommends the following for further studies: the SLM should undergo a try-out process to test its effectiveness in student learning, and further development and validation are highly recommended.

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